

ETU and OET: Thermal Indices for Integrated and Factor- and Segment-Resolved Evaluation

Kazuo NAGANO¹⁾ and Tetsumi HORIKOSHI²⁾

1) Kyoto Prefectural University, Ph.D., ORCID: 0000-0003-1924-1376

2) Unemployed, Dr. Eng.

Abstract

The ETVO thermal index was derived to incorporate solar radiation into the ETV on the basis of the human heat budget model, and a similar index, ETU, was derived to incorporate heat conduction into the ETVO and to enable adjustment to non-uniform environments. ETVO and ETU can represent the universal and separate effects of the environmental factors simultaneously, whereas ETU can indicate the effects on each body segment as well as the whole body. This article presents the theory underlying these two indices, presents some modifications to these indices, and also explains the OET index, in which the mathematical structure of ETU is retained while the standard environmental parameters are aligned with those of SET*.

1. Introduction

There are several thermal indices that consider six factors based on the human heat budget. The ET* and SET* indices (Gagge et al. 1971, 1986) represent the overall effects of these six factors, whereas ETV, proposed by Horikoshi et al. (1995), represents not only the overall effects but also the individual effects of longwave radiation, wind speed, and humidity simultaneously. Nagano and Horikoshi (2011a) derived the outdoor ETV (ETVO) index, which incorporates the effects of solar (shortwave) radiation while retaining the other characteristics of ETV. Nagano and Horikoshi (2011b) also developed the universal effective temperature (ETU) by incorporating the effects of conduction and hence segmental effects. We made minor revisions to ETVO and ETU following their initial publication, and then introduced a new index called OET (Nagano et al. 2020). This article explains the theory used to derive OET from ETV.

2. Mathematical Structure of ETV

This section outlines the structure of the basic ETV. The heat losses from the human body to the environment via convection and longwave radiation are denoted by C and R_L , respectively, and are expressed as follows:

$$C = h_c F_{cl} f_{cl} (t_{sk} - t_a) \quad (1)$$

$$R_L = h_r F_{cl} f_{cl} (t_{sk} - t_r) \quad (2)$$

$$F_{cl} = 1 / (1 + h f_{cl} R_{cl}) \quad (3)$$

$$h = h_c + h_r \quad (4)$$

where h_c : convective heat transfer coefficient, F_{cl} : thermal efficiency of clothing, f_{cl} : area factor for clothing, t_{sk} : skin temperature, t_a : air temperature, h_r : radiative heat transfer coefficient, t_r : mean radiant temperature, h : overall heat transfer coefficient, R_{cl} : basic thermal resistance of clothing.

Combining these gives the operative temperature (OT)

described by Winslow et al. (1937):

$$C + R_L = h F_{cl} f_{cl} (t_{sk} - OT) \quad (5)$$

$$OT = (h_c t_a + h_r t_r) / h \quad (6)$$

By transforming this OT, the effective longwave radiant field (ERFL) can be obtained. This is the same as the ERF proposed by Gagge et al. (1967), but this name is used as an explicit indication that it refers to the longwave component.

$$OT = t_a + \frac{ERFL}{h F_{cl} f_{cl}} \quad (7)$$

$$ERFL = h_r F_{cl} f_{cl} (t_r - t_a) \quad (8)$$

Equation (7) shows that the OT is a hypothetical air temperature that includes the effects of longwave radiation. The second term on the right-hand side expresses this effect as an effective temperature difference from the air temperature.

As an analogy to this effective radiant field, Horikoshi et al. (1991) defined an effective field for wind speed, which is derived by defining a wind-corrected air temperature t_v instead of OT. t_v is a hypothetical air temperature at which the convective heat loss in a standard environment is equal to that in the evaluated environment. Horikoshi et al. (1991) established standard environmental parameters as a wind speed of 0.1 m/s and clothing insulation of 0 clo.

$$C = h_c F_{cl} f_{cl} (t_{sk} - t_a) = h_{co} F_{clo} f_{clo} (t_{sk} - t_v) \quad (9)$$

$$t_v = t_a + \frac{TVF}{h_{co} F_{clo} f_{clo}} \quad (10)$$

$$TVF = (h_{co} F_{clo} f_{clo} - h_c F_{cl} f_{cl}) (t_{sk} - t_a) \quad (11)$$

where h_{co} : convective heat transfer coefficient in the standard environment (3.0 W/(m²K)), F_{clo} : thermal efficiency of clothing in the standard environment (with a value of one), f_{clo} : area factor of clothing in the standard environment (with a value of one).

The second term on the right-hand side of Equation (10) represents the effect of wind speed based on air temperature.

TVF is the thermal velocity field, and corresponds to ERFL for longwave radiation (Horikoshi et al. 1995).

The sum $C + R_L$ can be expressed based on Equations (2) and (9) as follows:

$$C + R_L = h_{co}F_{clo}f_{clo}(t_{sk} - t_v) + h_rF_{cl}f_{cl}(t_{sk} - t_r) = h_v(t_{sk} - OTV) \quad (12)$$

$$OTV = (h_{co}F_{clo}f_{clo}t_v + h_rF_{cl}f_{cl}t_r)/h_v = t_a + \frac{TVF}{h_v} + \frac{ERFL}{h_v} \quad (13)$$

$$h_v = h_{co}F_{clo}f_{clo} + h_rF_{cl}f_{cl} \quad (14)$$

OTV represents a hypothetical air temperature that incorporates the effects of wind speed and longwave radiation (Horikoshi et al. 1995).

Heat loss from the human body via evaporation E is expressed as follows:

$$E = wh'_e(p_{sk,s} - p_a) \quad (15)$$

$$h'_e = h_eF_{pcl}f_{cl} = h_cF_{pcl}f_{cl}LR = hF_{cl}f_{cl}i_mLR \quad (16)$$

where w : wettedness, $p_{sk,s}$: saturated water vapor pressure at t_{sk} , p_a : water vapor pressure at t_a , h_e : evaporative heat transfer coefficient, F_{pcl} : vapor permeability efficiency of clothing, LR: Lewis relation, i_m : clothing vapor permeation index.

Horikoshi et al. (1995) derived the ETV by adding this expression to Equation (12) and considering a trade-off between OTV and humidity, following Fobelets and Gagge (1988):

$$\begin{aligned} C + R_L + E &= h_v(t_{sk} - OTV) + wh'_e(p_{sk,s} - p_a) \\ &= h_v \left[\left(t_{sk} + \frac{wh'_e}{h_v} p_{sk,s} \right) - \left(OTV + \frac{wh'_e}{h_v} p_a \right) \right] \\ &= h_v \left[\left(t_{sk} + \frac{wh'_e}{h_v} p_{sk,s} \right) - \left(ETV + \frac{wh'_e}{2h_v} p_{ETV,s} \right) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

$$ETV = OTV + \frac{wh'_e}{h_v} (p_a - 0.5p_{ETV,s}) \quad (18)$$

where $p_{ETV,s}$: saturated water vapor pressure at ETV.

The second term on the right-hand side of Equation (18) represents the effective temperature difference due to humidity. Substituting Equation (13) into Equation (18) yields

$$ETV = t_a + \frac{TVF}{h_v} + \frac{ERFL}{h_v} + \frac{EHF}{h_v} \quad (19)$$

$$EHF = wh'_e(p_a - 0.5p_{ETV,s}) \quad (20)$$

EHF is the effective humid field, and represents the effect of humidity (Horikoshi et al. 1995). Thus, ETV is a hypothetical air temperature that incorporates the effects of wind speed, longwave radiation, and humidity. In this formulation, effective fields for wind speed and humidity are defined in an analogous way to the effective radiant field described by Gagge et al. (1967). Both the overall and individual effects are represented simultaneously by adding the effective temperature differences due to wind speed, longwave radiation, and humidity to the air temperature.

3. Consideration of Solar Heat

The solar irradiance J reaching the clothing surface is the sum of the direct and diffuse components:

$$J = f_{cl}f_pJ_{dn} + f_{cl}f_{rd} \sum_k \varphi_{cl-k} J_{dif-k} \quad (21)$$

where f_p : projected area factor, J_{dn} : direct normal solar irradiance, f_{rd} : effective radiation area factor, φ_{cl-k} : angle factor between the human body and surrounding surface k , J_{dif-k} : diffuse solar irradiance from surrounding surface k .

In order to incorporate this effect into the ETV, heat budget equations can be formulated for the skin surface and the outer surface of the clothing. The solar irradiance is reflected, absorbed, and transmitted at the clothing surface. The transmitted portion then undergoes repeated reflection, absorption, and transmission between the skin and clothing and within layers of clothing, and eventually converges (Siegel 1973; Kuwabara et al. 2009, 2010). Taking this multiple reflection into account and denoting the net solar absorptance incident on the skin surface as α_{skn} , the net solar heat gain at the skin surface is $\alpha_{skn}J$. Heat loss from the skin surface occurs through conduction from the skin to the clothing and through evaporation. Hence, the equation for the heat budget at the skin surface is as follows:

$$q_{sk} = (t_{sk} - t_{cl})/R_{cl} - \alpha_{skn}J + E \quad (22)$$

The net solar heat gain at the clothing surface is $\alpha_{cln}J$, where α_{cln} is the net solar absorptance of the clothing, taking into consideration multiple reflections. The heat losses from the clothing surface to the environment via convection and longwave radiation are denoted as \dot{C} and \dot{R}_L , respectively:

$$\dot{C} = h_c f_{cl}(t_{cl} - t_a) \quad (23)$$

$$\dot{R}_L = h_r f_{cl}(t_{cl} - t_r) \quad (24)$$

$$\dot{C} + \dot{R}_L = h f_{cl}(t_{cl} - OT) \quad (25)$$

The equation for the heat budget at the clothing surface is then as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} (t_{sk} - t_{cl})/R_{cl} &= \dot{C} + \dot{R}_L - \alpha_{cln}J \\ &= h f_{cl}(t_{cl} - OT) - \alpha_{cln}J \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

Solving Equation (26) for t_{cl} gives:

$$t_{cl} = F_{cl}t_{sk} + (1 - F_{cl})OT + F_{cl}R_{cl}\alpha_{cln}J \quad (27)$$

Substituting this into Equation (26) and eliminating t_{cl} yields the following equation:

$$\dot{C} + \dot{R}_L - \alpha_{cln}J = hF_{cl}f_{cl}(t_{sk} - OT) - F_{cl}\alpha_{cln}J \quad (28)$$

Substituting Equation (5) into the right-hand side yields:

$$\dot{C} + \dot{R}_L - \alpha_{cln}J = C + R_L - F_{cl}\alpha_{cln}J \quad (29)$$

Substituting Equation (26) into Equation (22) also gives the following equation:

$$q_{sk} = \dot{C} + \dot{R}_L - (\alpha_{cln} + \alpha_{skn})J + E \quad (30)$$

Substituting Equation (29) into this yields:

$$q_{sk} = C + R_L - (F_{cl}\alpha_{cln} + \alpha_{skn})J + E \quad (31)$$

The third term on the right-hand side of this equation is the net solar heat gain to the human body, and is denoted as R_S . When this is subtracted from Equation (12), we have:

$$R_S = (F_{cl}\alpha_{cln} + \alpha_{skn})J \quad (32)$$

$$\begin{aligned} C + R_L - R_S &= h_v(t_{sk} - OTV) - R_S \\ &= h_v(t_{sk} - OTVS) \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

$$\begin{aligned} OTVS &= OTV + \frac{R_S}{h_v} \\ &= t_a + \frac{TVF}{h_v} + \frac{ERFL}{h_v} + \frac{ERFS}{h_v} \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

$$ERFS = R_S = (F_{cl}\alpha_{cln} + \alpha_{skn})J \quad (35)$$

OTVS represents a hypothetical air temperature that incorporates the effects of wind speed, longwave radiation, and shortwave radiation. ERFS is the effective shortwave radiant field (Nagano and Horikoshi 2011a, 2016), representing the effect of shortwave radiation.

Nagano and Horikoshi (2011a) derived the ETVO index by incorporating the effect of humidity, following the same approach as for ETV:

$$\begin{aligned} ETVO &= OTVS + \frac{wh'_e}{h_v}(p_a - 0.5p_{ETVO,s}) \\ &= t_a + \frac{TVF}{h_v} + \frac{ERFL}{h_v} + \frac{ERFS}{h_v} + \frac{EHF}{h_v} \end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

$$EHF = wh'_e(p_a - 0.5p_{ETVO,s}) \quad (37)$$

where $p_{ETVO,s}$: saturated water vapor pressure at ETVO.

This shows that even when the solar radiation is incorporated, its effect is added as an effective temperature difference, thus preserving the ability of ETV to represent overall and individual effects simultaneously.

ETVO presented here (Nagano and Horikoshi 2016) treats solar heat gain more precisely than in its initial form (Nagano and Horikoshi 2011a), where solar heat gain in the initial publication was handled in a simplified manner as follows:

$$R_S = \alpha_{cl}J \quad (38)$$

where α_{cl} is the solar absorptance of the clothed human body, though in practice it was often assumed to be 0.7 (Weihs et al. 2012; Kurazumi et al. 2012; Watanabe et al. 2013) or taken as the solar absorptance of the outermost single piece of clothing (Nielsen 1990; Nagano and Horikoshi 2011a, 2011b). In other words, the solar radiation transmitted through clothing and the resulting multiple reflections are not considered. However, unless the transmittance of the outermost clothing is extremely small, the effect of multiple reflections cannot be ignored. In addition, F_{cl} is omitted from Equation (38); this is because, as is clear from Equations (30) and (31), the sum $C + R_L$ is treated as equal to $\dot{C} + \dot{R}_L$. Unless the clothing insulation is 0 clo, $F_{cl} < 1$, but if there is a transmitted portion, $\alpha_{cl} < \alpha_{cln}$ and $\alpha_{skn} > 0$. Hence, for evaluations in summer with less clothing, the effect of omitting F_{cl} may be offset, and Equation (38) may be acceptable, but for cases involving more clothing, F_{cl} becomes very small, making it easy to overestimate solar radiation. ETVO, ETU and ETFe, an index proposed by Kurazumi et al. (2011), use Equation (38), but it would be

desirable to adopt Equation (32) for a more precise evaluation.

4. Redefinition of Heat Transfer Coefficient

Before incorporating the effect of conduction into ETVO to derive ETU, the heat transfer coefficient h_v is redefined. For this purpose, a radiant heat transfer coefficient of 4.5 W/(m²K), a value typical of indoor environments, is adopted as the standard. A hypothetical radiant temperature t_{rv} is defined such that the longwave radiation heat loss in the standard environment is equal to that in the evaluated environment.

$$\begin{aligned} R_L &= h_r F_{cl} f_{cl} (t_{sk} - t_r) \\ &= h_{ro} F_{clo} f_{clo} (t_{sk} - t_{rv}) \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

where h_{ro} : radiant heat transfer coefficient in the standard environment (with a value of 4.5 or 4.7 ε_h W/(m²K), ε_h : longwave emissivity of the human body (with a value of 0.95).

Equation (12) is replaced by Equation (39) and rearranged as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} C + R_L &= h_{co} F_{clo} f_{clo} (t_{sk} - t_v) \\ &\quad + h_{ro} F_{clo} f_{clo} (t_{sk} - t_{rv}) \\ &= h_v (t_{sk} - OTV) \end{aligned} \quad (40)$$

$$\begin{aligned} OTV &= (h_{co} F_{clo} f_{clo} t_v + h_{ro} F_{clo} f_{clo} t_{rv}) / h_v \\ &= t_a + \frac{TVF}{h_v} + \frac{SERFL}{h_v} \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

$$h_v = h_{co} F_{clo} f_{clo} + h_{ro} F_{clo} f_{clo} \quad (42)$$

$$SERFL = h_{ro} F_{clo} f_{clo} (t_{rv} - t_a) \quad (43)$$

Accordingly, h_v is redefined as a constant of 7.5 W/(m²K) based on the standard environment. The longwave effective radiant field is also revised based on the standard environment, and is called the standard effective longwave radiant field (SERFL) (Nagano and Horikoshi 2011b). Since OTV in Equation (13) has been revised to give Equation (41), OTVS in Equation (34) is also revised as follows:

$$OTVS = t_a + \frac{TVF}{h_v} + \frac{SERFL}{h_v} + \frac{ERFS}{h_v} \quad (44)$$

Analogously to t_{rv} , a hypothetical vapor pressure p_v is defined such that the evaporative heat loss in the standard environment is equal to that in the evaluated environment.

$$E = wh'_e(p_{sk,s} - p_a) = wh_{eo}(p_{sk,s} - p_v) \quad (45)$$

where h_{eo} : evaporative heat transfer coefficient in the standard environment.

Equation (36) can be rewritten using Equations (44) and (45) to give:

$$\begin{aligned} ETVO &= OTVS + \frac{wh_{eo}}{h_v}(p_v - 0.5p_{ETVO,s}) \\ &= t_a + \frac{TVF}{h_v} + \frac{SERFL}{h_v} + \frac{ERFS}{h_v} + \frac{SEHF}{h_v} \end{aligned} \quad (46)$$

$$SEHF = wh_{eo}(p_v - 0.5p_{ETVO,s}) \quad (47)$$

The effective humid field is also revised based on the standard environment to give the standard effective humid field (SEHF)

(Nagano and Horikoshi 2011b). Since h_v has been redefined, ETVO is revised from Equation (36) to Equation (46), meaning that the values differ accordingly.

Equations (43) and (47) can be rearranged as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{SERFL} &= h_{ro}F_{clo}f_{clo}(t_r - t_a) \\ &+ h_{ro}F_{clo}f_{clo}(t_{rv} - t_r) \end{aligned} \quad (48)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{SEHF} &= wh_{eo}(p_a - 0.5p_{\text{ETVO},s}) \\ &+ wh_{eo}(p_v - p_a) \end{aligned} \quad (49)$$

Note that in the initial publication by Nagano and Horikoshi (2011b), the first terms on the right-hand sides of these two equations were defined as SERFL and SEHF, and the second terms were given as separate effective fields, TVFr and TVFe, representing the effects of differences in the mean radiant temperature and water vapor pressure between the standard and evaluated environments. Since these are essentially parts of the longwave radiation and evaporation effects, TVFr and TVFe are incorporated here into SERFL and SEHF, respectively, and the combined terms retain these names.

5. Consideration of Heat Conduction

The surface of human skin is divided into non-contact and contact areas, and the effect of heat conduction in the contact areas is considered. Letting f_n denotes the ratio of the non-contact area to the whole skin surface, then the heat budget equation for the non-contact part becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} C + R_L - R_S + E &= h_v f_n (t_{sk} - \text{OTVS}) \\ &+ wh_{eo} f_n (p_{sk,s} - p_v) \\ &= h_v f_n \left[(t_{sk} + \frac{wh_{eo}}{h_v} p_{sk,s}) - (\text{OTVS} + \frac{wh_{eo}}{h_v} p_v) \right] \\ &= h_v f_n \left[(t_{sk} + \frac{wh_{eo}}{h_v} p_{sk,s}) \right. \\ &\quad \left. - (\text{ETVO} + \frac{wh_{eo}}{2h_v} p_{\text{ETVO},s}) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (50)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{ETVO} &= \text{OTVS} + \frac{wh_{eo} f_n}{h_v f_n} (p_v - 0.5p_{\text{ETVO},s}) \\ &= t_a + \frac{\text{TVF}}{h_v f_n} + \frac{\text{SERFL}}{h_v f_n} + \frac{\text{ERFS}}{h_v f_n} + \frac{\text{SEHF}}{h_v f_n} \end{aligned} \quad (51)$$

$$\text{TVF} = h_{co} F_{clo} f_{clo} f_n (t_v - t_a) \quad (52)$$

$$\text{SERFL} = h_{ro} F_{clo} f_{clo} f_n (t_{rv} - t_a) \quad (53)$$

$$\text{ERFS} = (F_{cl} \alpha_{cln} + \alpha_{skn}) f_n J \quad (54)$$

$$\text{SEHF} = wh_{eo} f_n (p_v - 0.5p_{\text{ETVO},s}) \quad (55)$$

In other words, all effective fields are multiplied by f_n , but since they are divided by $h_v f_n$, ETVO is consistent with Equation (46).

q_d is introduced as the heat loss conducted from the skin surface to the material in the contact part, as follows:

$$q_d = \frac{\lambda}{l} F_{clid} (t_{skd} - t_b) \quad (56)$$

where λ : thermal conductivity of the contact material, l : thickness of the contact material, F_{clid} : thermal efficiency of

clothing due to conduction, t_{skd} : skin temperature of the contact area, t_b : surface temperature of the material on the side opposite to the contact surface.

Following Kurazumi et al. (2010, 2011), t_{skd} is replaced with t_{sk} and t_b with t_a , with the latter representing the material surface temperature on the contact side. The heat loss from the human skin surface by conduction, C_d , is then as follows:

$$C_d = q_d f_d = h_d F_{clid} f_d (t_{sk} - t_a) \quad (57)$$

$$h_d = \frac{q_d}{F_{clid}(t_{sk}-t_a)} = \frac{\lambda(t_{skd}-t_b)}{l(t_{sk}-t_a)} \quad (58)$$

where f_d : ratio of the contact area to the whole skin surface.

A hypothetical material surface temperature t_{do} is defined such that the conductive heat loss when in contact with the standard material under a standard environment is equal to that in the evaluated environment:

$$C_d = q_d f_d = h_{do} f_d (t_{sk} - t_{do}) \quad (59)$$

where h_{do} : thermal conductance of the standard material (7.5 W/(m²K)).

The total sensible heat loss, including this conductive heat loss, is given by the following equation:

$$\begin{aligned} C + R_L - R_S + C_d &= h_v f_n (t_{sk} - \text{OTVS}) \\ &+ h_{do} f_d (t_{sk} - t_{do}) \\ &= h_u (t_{sk} - \text{OTVSC}) \end{aligned} \quad (60)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{OTVSC} &= \frac{h_v f_n \text{OTVS} + h_{do} f_d t_{do}}{h_u} \\ &= t_a + \frac{\text{TVF}}{h_u} + \frac{\text{SERFL}}{h_u} + \frac{\text{ERFS}}{h_u} + \frac{\text{SECF}}{h_u} \end{aligned} \quad (61)$$

$$h_u = h_v f_n + h_{do} f_d \quad (62)$$

$$\text{SECF} = h_{do} f_d (t_{do} - t_a) \quad (63)$$

By definition, h_v and h_{do} are both 7.5 W/(m²K), and f_n + f_d = 1, from which we find that h_u is a constant at 7.5 W/(m²K). OTVSC represents a hypothetical air temperature that incorporates the effects of wind speed, longwave radiation, shortwave radiation, and conduction. SECF is the standard effective conduction field (Nagano and Horikoshi 2011b), representing the effect of conduction based on the standard material. This is also expressed as an effective temperature difference that is added to the air temperature.

The effect of humidity is considered in the same manner as described above:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{ETVSC} &= \text{OTVSC} + \frac{wh_{eo} f_n}{h_u} (p_a - 0.5p_{\text{ETVSC},s}) \\ &= t_a + \frac{\text{TVF}}{h_u} + \frac{\text{SERFL}}{h_u} + \frac{\text{ERFS}}{h_u} + \frac{\text{SECF}}{h_u} + \frac{\text{SEHF}}{h_u} \end{aligned} \quad (64)$$

where $p_{\text{ETVSC},s}$: saturated water vapor pressure at ETVSC.

ETVSC represents a hypothetical air temperature that incorporates the effects of wind speed, longwave radiation, shortwave radiation, conduction, and humidity.

6. Consideration of a Non-uniform Thermal Environment

The effective fields presented above represent the effects of each thermal environmental factor on the whole human body. These are now divided to represent the effects on each segment of the body. To do this, heat budget equations are formulated by dividing the non-contact and contact areas of the human skin surface into i and j segments, respectively. The heat losses from segment i to the environment via convection, longwave radiation, and evaporation are C_i , R_{Li} , and E_i , respectively:

$$C_i = h_{ci}F_{cli}f_{cli}f_i(t_{ski} - t_{ai}) \quad (65)$$

$$R_{Li} = h_{ri}F_{cli}f_{cli}f_i(t_{ski} - t_{ri}) \quad (66)$$

$$E_i = w_i h'_{ei} f_i (p_{ski,s} - p_{ai}) \quad (67)$$

where h_{ci} : convective heat transfer coefficient for segment i , F_{cli} : effective thermal efficiency of clothing for segment i , f_{cli} : area factor of clothing for segment i , f_i : area ratio of segment i to the whole skin surface, t_{ski} : skin temperature of segment i , t_{ai} : air temperature around segment i , h_{ri} : radiant heat transfer coefficient for segment i , t_{ri} : mean radiant temperature for segment i , w_i : wettedness of segment i , h'_{ei} : evaporative heat transfer coefficient, including clothing effects, for segment i , $p_{ski,s}$: saturated water vapor pressure at t_{ski} , p_{ai} : water vapor pressure around segment i .

We can replace t_{ski} with t_{sk} , $p_{ski,s}$ with $p_{sk,s}$, and w_i with w in Equations (65) to (67), meaning that C_i , R_{Li} , and E_i are given by the following equations:

$$C_i = H_{ci}F_{cli}f_{cli}f_i(t_{sk} - t_{ai}) \quad (68)$$

$$R_{Li} = H_{ri}F_{cli}f_{cli}f_i(t_{sk} - t_{ri}) \quad (69)$$

$$E_i = wH'_{ei}f_i(p_{sk,s} - p_{ai}) \quad (70)$$

$$H_{ci} = h_{ci} \frac{t_{ski} - t_{ai}}{t_{sk} - t_{ai}} \quad (71)$$

$$H_{ri} = h_{ri} \frac{t_{ski} - t_{ri}}{t_{sk} - t_{ri}} \quad (72)$$

$$H'_{ei} = h'_{ei} \frac{p_{ski,s} - p_{ai}}{p_{sk} - p_{ai}} \cdot \frac{w_i}{w} \quad (73)$$

Similarly to Equations (9), (39), and (45), the hypothetical air temperature t_{vi} , hypothetical radiant temperature t_{rvi} , and hypothetical vapor pressure p_{vi} for segment i are defined such that the heat losses via convection, longwave radiation, and evaporation in the standard environment are equal to those in the evaluated environment:

$$C_i = h_{co}F_{clo}f_{clo}f_i(t_{sk} - t_{vi}) \quad (74)$$

$$R_{Li} = h_{ro}F_{clo}f_{clo}f_i(t_{sk} - t_{rvi}) \quad (75)$$

$$E_i = wh_{eo}f_i(p_{sk,s} - p_{vi}) \quad (76)$$

R_{Si} is introduced as the net solar heat gain for segment i :

$$R_{Si} = (F_{cli}\alpha_{cni} + \alpha_{skni})f_i J_i \quad (77)$$

$$J_i = f_{cli}f_{pi}J_{dni} + f_{cli}f_{rai} \sum_k \varphi_{cli-k} J_{difi-k} \quad (78)$$

where α_{cni} : net solar absorptance of clothing for segment i , α_{skni} : net solar absorptance of skin surface for segment i , f_{pi} : projected area factor for segment i , J_{dni} : direct normal solar irradiance for segment i , f_{rai} : effective radiation area factor for

segment i , φ_{cli-k} : angle factor between segment i and the surrounding surface k , J_{difi-k} : diffuse solar irradiance from the surrounding surface k to segment i .

Using the same approach as described above, the hypothetical air temperature for segment i OTVSi is derived.

$$C_i + R_{Li} - R_{Si} = h_v f_i (t_{sk} - \text{OTVSi}) \quad (79)$$

$$\text{OTVSi} = t_{ai} + \frac{\text{TVFi}}{h_v f_i} + \frac{\text{SERFLi}}{h_v f_i} + \frac{\text{ERFSi}}{h_v f_i} \quad (80)$$

$$\text{TVFi} = h_{co}F_{clo}f_{clo}f_i(t_{vi} - t_{ai}) \quad (81)$$

$$\text{SERFLi} = h_{ro}F_{clo}f_{clo}f_i(t_{rvi} - t_{ai}) \quad (82)$$

$$\text{ERFSi} = (F_{cli}\alpha_{cni} + \alpha_{skni})f_i J_i \quad (83)$$

Using these expressions, the sensible heat loss from the non-contact parts of the whole body is obtained.

$$C + R_L - R_S = \sum_i (C_i + R_{Li} - R_{Si}) \quad (84)$$

That is,

$$h_v f_n (t_{sk} - \text{OTVS}) = \sum_i h_v f_i (t_{sk} - \text{OTVSi}) \quad (85)$$

Since f_i is the area ratio between the non-contact segment i and the whole skin surface, the following equation holds:

$$f_n = \sum_i f_i \quad (86)$$

Hence, OTVS is expressed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{OTVS} &= \frac{\sum_i h_v f_i \text{OTVSi}}{h_v f_n} \\ &= \sum_i h_v f_i t_{ai} + \frac{\sum_i \text{TVFi}}{h_v f_n} + \frac{\sum_i \text{SERFLi}}{h_v f_n} + \frac{\sum_i \text{ERFSi}}{h_v f_n} \end{aligned} \quad (87)$$

A representative air temperature t_{ao} is introduced, and Equation (87) is rewritten as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{OTVS} &= t_{ao} + \frac{\sum_i \text{EATFi}}{h_v f_n} + \frac{\sum_i \text{TVFi}}{h_v f_n} + \frac{\sum_i \text{SERFLi}}{h_v f_n} \\ &\quad + \frac{\sum_i \text{ERFSi}}{h_v f_n} \end{aligned} \quad (88)$$

$$\text{EATFi} = h_v f_i (t_{ai} - t_{ao}) \quad (89)$$

EATFi is the effective air temperature field, which represents the effect caused by the difference between the representative air temperature and the air temperature around segment i . The representative air temperature can be set based on the target and purpose of the evaluation, such as the air temperature around a specific segment or the mean air temperature.

Note that in the initial publication by Nagano and Horikoshi (2011b) on ETU, EATF was called the non-uniform air temperature field (NUATF), as it was intended for evaluating environments with air temperature non-uniformity. However, for example, if the air temperature at which PMV = 0 is taken as the representative air temperature, even in a uniform environment, the effect of air temperature deviation in the evaluated environment can be evaluated relative to the thermally neutral air temperature. Hence, ETVO can also be expressed using EATF (Nagano and Horikoshi 2016) as follows:

$$\text{ETVO} = t_{ao} + \frac{\text{EATF}}{h_v} + \frac{\text{TVF}}{h_v} + \frac{\text{ERFL}}{h_v} + \frac{\text{ERFS}}{h_v} + \frac{\text{EHF}}{h_v} \quad (90)$$

$$\text{EATF} = h_v (t_a - t_{ao}) \quad (91)$$

The heat loss from contact segment j via conduction C_{dj} is given by the following equation, in the same manner as for Equations (56) to (59):

$$C_{dj} = h_{do}f_j(t_{sk} - t_{doj}) \quad (92)$$

Since f_j is the area ratio of contact segment j to the whole skin surface, the following equation holds:

$$f_d = \sum_j f_j \quad (93)$$

Summing Equation (92) over all contact parts and adding the heat loss from the non-contact parts yields the total sensible heat loss from the whole body:

$$\begin{aligned} C + R_L - R_S + C_d &= h_v f_n (t_{sk} - OTVS) \\ &+ \sum_j h_{do} f_j (t_{sk} - t_{doj}) \\ &= h_u (t_{sk} - OTVSC) \end{aligned} \quad (94)$$

$$\begin{aligned} OTVSC &= \frac{h_v f_n OTVS + \sum_j h_{do} f_j t_{doj}}{h_u} \\ &= t_{ao} + \frac{\sum_i EATFi}{h_u} + \frac{\sum_i TVFi}{h_u} + \frac{\sum_i SERFLi}{h_u} \\ &+ \frac{\sum_i ERFSi}{h_u} + \frac{\sum_j SECFj}{h_u} \end{aligned} \quad (95)$$

$$h_u = h_v f_n + \sum_i h_{do} f_j = h_v f_n + h_{do} f_d \quad (96)$$

$$SECFj = h_{do} f_j (t_{doj} - t_{ao}) \quad (97)$$

From Equation (93), we see that h_u in Equation (96) is consistent with h_u in Equation (62). Furthermore, by considering the effect of humidity in the same manner as described above, ETU is derived (Nagano and Horikoshi 2011b) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} C + R_L - R_S + C_d + E &= h_u (t_{sk} - OTVSC) \\ &+ \sum_i E_i \\ &= h_u \left[(t_{sk} + \sum_i \frac{wh_{eofi}}{h_u} p_{sk,s}) \right. \\ &\left. - (OTVSC + \sum_i \frac{wh_{eofi}}{h_u} p_{vi}) \right] \\ &= h_u \left[(t_{sk} + \sum_i \frac{wh_{eofi}}{h_u} p_{sk,s}) \right. \\ &\left. - (ETU + \sum_i \frac{wh_{eofi}}{2h_u} p_{ETU,s}) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (98)$$

$$\begin{aligned} ETU &= OTVSC + \sum_i \frac{wh_{eofi}}{h_u} (p_{vi} - 0.5p_{ETU,s}) \\ &= t_{ao} + \frac{\sum_i EATFi}{h_u} + \frac{\sum_i TVFi}{h_u} + \frac{\sum_i SERFLi}{h_u} \\ &+ \frac{\sum_i ERFSi}{h_u} + \frac{\sum_i SEHFi}{h_u} + \frac{\sum_j SECFj}{h_u} \end{aligned} \quad (99)$$

$$SEHFi = wh_{eofi} (p_{vi} - 0.5p_{ETU,s}) \quad (100)$$

where $p_{ETU,s}$: saturated water vapor pressure at ETU.

Thus, each effective field is divided by segment, and ETU is calculated as their sum. This allows the impact of the surrounding thermal environment to be expressed as individual effective temperature differences even when the environment differs for each body segment.

7. Aligning ETU with SET*

When Gagge et al. (1971) first published SET*, they used a clothing insulation of 0.6 clo as one of the standard environmental parameters. Although this was later modified to allow for fine-tuning based on the activity level, the value remains around 0.6 clo (Gagge et al. 1986), based on the clo value of the KSU (Kansas State University) uniform (McNall et al. 1968), which was widely used in numerous experiments at the time. Since it represents neither extremely heavy nor light clothing, it can reasonably be considered a representative value for intermediate seasons. However, in other countries and regions with different climatic characteristics and clothing cultures, this value may not be representative. It is therefore debatable whether this value is sufficient as a universal standard (Horikoshi and Kobayashi 1985).

By contrast, 0 clo (the unclothed state) is taken as standard for ETU. This is not a value inferred from empirical observation, but an absolute boundary condition in which the clothing is physically absent (Horikoshi and Kobayashi, 1985). Zero is the one self-evident, assumption-free origin that is not dependent on cultural or geographical context, and it is precisely this universality that gives it significance as a reference point.

This is not a matter of one index being superior to another, but rather a difference in design philosophy, and more specifically in what constitutes an appropriate standard. However, this difference in the standard clothing insulation is the primary reason why the SET* and ETU yield different values when used to evaluate the same thermal environment. To address this issue, Nagano et al. (2020) proposed the OET (occupied effective temperature) index, in which all standard environmental parameters of ETU, including clothing insulation, are replaced with those of SET*. OET matches SET* when the two-node model is applied, making it easier to compare OET with numerous studies that have used SET* in the past, and to refer to various findings related to SET*. This is one advantage of OET that was difficult to achieve with ETU. In addition, OET makes it possible to evaluate the effects of different environmental elements and different body parts, which was difficult with the classic SET*.

8. Conclusion

The derivations of ETVO, ETU and OET from ETV have been described, and the solar heat gain, which was initially expressed simply as in Equation (38), was presented more precisely in Equation (32). In addition, the SERFL and SEHF were modified from their initial forms. The original name of NUATF (non-uniform air temperature field) was also changed to EATF (effective air temperature field).

Finally, ETVO and its constituent terms can be summarized as follows:

$$ETVO = t_{ao} + \frac{EATF}{h_v} + \frac{TVF}{h_v} + \frac{ERFL}{h_v} + \frac{ERFS}{h_v} + \frac{EHF}{h_v} \quad (90)$$

$$EATF = h_v(t_a - t_{ao}) \quad (91)$$

$$TVF = (h_{co}F_{clo}f_{clo} - h_cF_{cl}f_{cl})(t_{sk} - t_a) \quad (11)$$

$$ERFL = h_rF_{cl}f_{cl}(t_r - t_a) \quad (8)$$

$$ERFS = (F_{cl}\alpha_{cln} + \alpha_{skn})J \quad (35)$$

$$EHF = wh'_e(p_a - 0.5p_{ETVO,s}) \quad (37)$$

$$h_v = h_{co}F_{clo}f_{clo} + h_rF_{cl}f_{cl} \quad (14)$$

ETU and its constituent terms can be summarized as follows:

$$ETU = t_{ao} + \frac{\sum_i EATFi}{h_u} + \frac{\sum_i TVFi}{h_u} + \frac{\sum_i SERFLi}{h_u} + \frac{\sum_i ERFSi}{h_u} + \frac{\sum_i SEHFi}{h_u} + \frac{\sum_j SECFj}{h_u} \quad (99)$$

$$EATFi = h_v f_i(t_{ai} - t_{ao}) \quad (89)$$

$$TVFi = h_{co}F_{clo}f_{clo}f_i(t_{vi} - t_{ai}) \quad (81)$$

$$SERFLi = h_{ro}F_{clo}f_{clo}f_i(t_{rvi} - t_{ai}) \quad (82)$$

$$ERFSi = (F_{cli}\alpha_{clni} + \alpha_{skni})f_i J_i \quad (83)$$

$$SEHFi = wh_{eo}f_i(p_{vi} - 0.5p_{ETU,s}) \quad (100)$$

$$SECFj = h_{do}f_j(t_{doj} - t_{ao}) \quad (97)$$

$$h_v = h_{co}F_{clo}f_{clo} + h_{ro}F_{clo}f_{clo} \quad (42)$$

$$h_u = h_v f_n + h_{do}f_d \quad (62)$$

The mathematical structure of OET is exactly the same for ETU: all that is needed is to replace the letters “ETU” in Equations (99) and (100) with “OET”.

Calculation programs for ETU and OET are available at <https://github.com/atelierkumori/TICalc> (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20568842).

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